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Application of ICT Tools to Enhance Cognitive Skills of Teenage Orphans

Dr. Waheed Shafiah

Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
VNR Vignana Jyothi Institute of Engineering & Technology,
Telangana, Hyderabad, India.

&

Dr. Raja Kumar

Assistant Professor,
Dept. of English,
Sheshadi Rao Gudlavalleru Engineering College,
Gudlavalleru, Andhra.

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Abstract:

Of many manifestations, COVID-19 has brought many fluctuations in the world economy and the standard of living in rural areas especially. Many lost their jobs; children became orphans women turned into single parents overnight and some were hospitalized. Despite all these problems, growth and development must continue if the world has to progress. As citizens of India, the responsibility is shouldered on everyone for the country's development. The need of the hour is that rural societies must be focused on the wide-ranging development of the world. Therefore, the paper has come up with an innovative idea to extend help in improving the quality of life of rural children, especially in the marginalized sector of the community. Orphans have less possibility of getting exposure through ICT tools of the teaching-learning process as there is a lot of difference in the education system between private school children and orphan schools for many reasons. So, to reduce the gap the paper wants to focus on the marginalized sector of the rural community teenage orphans of Telangana region as a challenge study for improving their living standards. For every child, skills are very important especially communication, cognitive, and logical reasoning. All children are not fortunate to acquire education and skills in the same manner. Some children are exposed to the environment of learning these abilities on par with the education and some of them do not get even the basic education. Hence, the study wants to illuminate the teenage orphans of the

Telangana region to improve their communication and cognitive skills. If teenage children's minds are ignited, then they will become better citizens tomorrow. Hence, teaching skills through ICT tools like LCD projectors, smartphone videos, power point presentations would be appropriate. If education is provided with ICT tools to teenage orphans, then they will acquire communication skills, cognitive skills, and confidence easily in less period. Added to it, orphans would acquire new exposure to learning through ICT methods. They would improve their personality development, become more eloquent in speaking the English language, awareness of online learning, and the importance of English and its opportunities. They may become more career-oriented, and participate in programs efficiently. All these inputs improve their cognitive skills and finally their standard of living. On the whole, there would be a holistic development for all the segregated children according to the National Education Policy and can raise their standard of living.

Keywords: ICT Tools, communication skills, cognitive skills, orphans, improved standard of living.

Introduction

The research wants to improve the standard of living of the rural Telangana region's teenage Orphans. The findings of the Telangana region show that seventy-one orphanages provide food, shelter, and basic education for the children. Basic education is also imparted by conducting classes in their premises and some of the orphanages, orphans are being sent to other schools in their locality. The research has been collected on the system of education that is provided to the orphans by doing interviews to the in-charge of the orphanages. Based on the provided information that has been obtained from orphanages is taken for research study in which the gap is identified that the orphans are lacking proper teaching-learning skills with ICT tools.

The comparative study is done between the standard of education of orphans and children in private schools. The study shows that orphans receive a higher standard of education than private school children because orphanages lack technological facilities. Orphanages cannot afford technical gadgets and at the same time, they are not aware of the importance of innovative methods of technical education. Orphans have little exposure to the importance of communication skills, cognitive skills, personality development, and the usage of the latest technological education and its benefits.

After identifying some of the loopholes in the education system of orphans, the research has decided to take up teenage orphans as an experimental study. They would be taught by technological gadgets like LCD projectors, and smartphones and teaching through videos, and PowerPoint presentations. As orphans are not aware of cognitive skills, personality development, and communication skills in English and their importance and opportunities, the research wants to create awareness among the orphans. In addition to that, the teenage orphans would be provided with essential Spoken English Websites.

The findings are that orphans would acquire new exposure to learning through ICT methods and improve their personality development, become more confident in speaking the English language, awareness of online learning, importance of English and its opportunities. They become more career-oriented and participate in speaking skills confidently. All these inputs definitely would improve their confidence, communication skills in English, cognitive skills & finally their standard of living.

Background

Many children are in orphanages throughout the world. Though they are protected for the sake of protection utmost care is not taken definitely. The most valuable precious gift “Mother” is lost in their lives. No one could replace in their mother’s place. Their life is very miserable once cannot imagine their situation. Many of them undergo psychological trauma because of physical mental, and emotional abuses. They need to work very hard to become a successful person in their lives. Some of them may have very good skills but they have to be directed with proper guidance.

A glimpse of the history of orphans during the seventeenth century showed that there were child welfare policies. George Whitefield (1714–1770), was a charismatic leader who had traveled to America to take care of orphaned children. Bethesda Orphanage, known as the House of Mercy was the first orphanage in the British American colonies in 1740. In 1801 seven orphan asylums were started in the Atlantic Coast. In 1790 only publicly funded orphanages were in the United States. Later, private associations began to appear in northern urban areas. Asylum offered short-term facilities as well as long-term care for impoverished mothers during economic downturns. They admitted ninety to one hundred children, boys under the age of six and girls under eight. All efforts were made to educate them. Orphans were instructed in reading, writing, and arithmetic. By the end of the 19th century, orphanages were considered one of the best methods for caring for children. Many poor single parents. preferred

to leave their children in orphanages. In New Jersey orphans were given many facilities with the help of supporters, championing the educational benefits, permanency, and stability. Children's Rights critics argue that "efforts should be focused on improving the foster care system instead of "institutionalizing" foster children." They were concerned about the emotional and cognitive development of children in orphanages.

With the help of the background history of the orphans their education system, and facilities, their cognitive skills motivated them to put forward for the study because today's children are tomorrow's citizens. The study has decided to take the rural areas of Telangana orphans. There are seventy-one orphanages like *Care and Love Orphanage*, *Bass Orphan Home*, *Asha Kuteer Orphanage*, *Amma Odi Orphanage*, *Darul Yathama Orphanage*, *Shia Orphanage*, *Anees-Ul-Gurba Orphanage* and so on. Telangana region orphanages' basic information has been taken with the help of in-charge of the orphanages about the system of education which is provided to them. Later in comparative study is done with their compatriots of private school children. The study found that orphans need attention & care to improve their standard of living.

Literature Survey

According to the (2005 Horizon Report), the following technical domains have the potential to contribute to the field of education. First, Extended learning involves improving conventional instruction and learning using contemporary communication tools or social networking sites. The method of instruction and gaining knowledge is no longer limited to the classroom but it has been extended beyond the classroom through social media platforms, that allow students to communicate with one another which "facilitates collaborative discussion, exchange of opinions, and critical thinking" (Huang, Hung, & Cheng, 2012).

Secondly, Ubiquitous Wireless which focuses on "the increasing penetration of wireless networks" (Jung, 2006), enables students to use mobile or portable devices, such as tablets, laptops, mobile phones, and other similar devices. Thirdly, Intelligent Searching, helps the educator to effectively find, arrange, and retrieve information. Finally, Educational Gaming, which includes simulations and games is seen as a knowledge-acquiring tool with positive impacts on critical thinking, motivation, problem-solving skills, and communication. (Jung, 2006). (Collis & Moonen, 2001) classified ICT applications into three categories: "learning resources," which include educational software, online resources, and video resources, "instructional organization of learning," which includes software and technology

tools for lecturing in the classroom, and the “Learning course management system” such as Moodle, Canvas, Computer-based testing systems, such as Hot Potatoes, and communication, which includes email systems and websites that provide communication possibilities.

The main goal is the implementation of ICT tools in the teaching-learning process. Detailed explanations can be given for better and quick understanding. Orphans' teenage children feel interested to learn through ICT tools. Imparting knowledge in the right method as per the enhancement of technology is the main challenge. The primary goal is to provide students with a broad context of LSRW skills. It can be mastered quickly with ICT tools to create more effective learning aids (R Bhushan, 2020) and A.Dash & KKuddus 2020).

Moreover, knowledge of differences in elements of cognitive abilities can provide a basis for the informed structuring of collaborative teams. Whilst some learners are capable of individually invoking the concerted activity of simultaneous and successive processing abilities, others may fully realize their potential only in concerted collaboration with others of complementary cognitive profiles. The provision of systemic programming supports, i.e. cognitive artifacts (Norman, 1991), to supplement simultaneous or successive abilities would serve a similar function and facilitate the realization of the computer as a collaborator.

The study on orphans took place in different places in different situations:

1. “Marginalised Elders: A Comparative Study of Rural and Urban Elders in Udaipur”.
2. “Rajasthan Problems and Prospect of Women Education in East Kameng District of Arunachal Pradesh”.
3. “Study on Employability Skills of Engineering Graduates: An Education Beyond University Scheme for Backward Class, Poor Learners, and Minority Students”.

The present study varies from others as no study has been done on developing the cognitive abilities of orphans with ICT tools. The marginalized orphans should also receive equal education along with their compatriots.

Problem Statement

Based on the study of developing the standard of living of rural Telangana region’s teenage orphans, the research wants to know the conditions of teenage orphans in Telangana. The findings of the Telangana region show that seventy-one orphanages provide basic education. When teenage orphans are compared with their compatriots in other private

schools, alarmingly the orphans need to be focused immediately as their standard of education is less. There is a lot of disparity in the standard of education between orphans and private school children. This variation may affect in development of their cognitive skills as well as their standard of living. So the research wants to take up the challenging task of providing what they are lacking in their present education system.

Orphans have less possibility of acquiring knowledge of the teaching-learning process through ICT tools. There is a lot of difference in the education system between private school children and the education received by orphans because of many reasons. So to reduce the gap the research study wants to focus on the marginalized sector of the rural community teenage orphans of Telangana region as a challenge study for improving the living standards. For every child, skills are very important especially communication skills, cognitive skills, and overall personality. All children are not fortunate to acquire education and skills in the same manner. Some children are exposed to the environment of learning all skills on par with the education and some of them do not get even basic education.

Objectives:

1. To impart Education through ICT tools with the latest innovative methods.
2. To develop their self-confidence and improve their communication skills in English.
3. To enhance their cognitive skills.

Methodology

As the orphanages cannot provide technological facilities like LCD, projector, Smart Phones, and the latest innovative teaching-learning technological education, the study tries to fill the gap by imparting education through using ICT Tools to create awareness of the private school education system. At the same time, many orphans lack communication skills in English due to hesitation, shyness, and with inferiority complex. The research would focus on developing their communication skills in English through ICT tools and enhancing their personality development, cognitive Skills their standard of living.

In this technological revolution, all should be aware of using technology in the modern education system. It creates an interest among children to learn more and more that would develop an inquisitive nature. Nurturing the idea of imparting technical skills through ICT tools

is the first step of success and it would be a last impression on them. Later, they acquire an independent habit of learning.

According to Van Laar and colleagues, digital communication skills encompass appropriate and effective communication using digital means. While teenage children do not communicate, so the familiarization of using ICT devices in appropriate ways may support early prerequisites and later can build communication skills.

Through ICT tools, the teaching-learning methodology is:

1. First, teenage orphans will be given an awareness of ICT tools in the teaching-learning process.
2. Related to their syllabus and course of education, videos will be displayed.
3. Spoken English Websites will be sent to them to practice their communication skills.
4. Inspirational videos will be shown.
5. Storytelling activities will be conducted after showing stories like Hellen Keller's 'The Story of My Life' and Pursuit of Happiness along with subtitles.
6. Self Introduction Videos will be projected and ask them to note down points in their notebooks.
7. Confidence-building stories will be shown to develop their confidence.

Outcome:

The expected outcomes are:

1. Orphans get new exposure to learning through ICT tools.
2. To reduce the education gap between orphan schools and private schools.
3. To enhance their cognitive and overall personality.
4. They would become more confident in English speaking skills.
5. To develop holistic development and to raise the standard of living.

Conclusion

Technology should be used by all educated people in every aspect of life and it has become the basic necessary tool. It plays an important role for everybody in every corner of the society.

In this 21st century, the teaching-learning process should be advanced and it should be on par with the advancement of technology at present. Most private schools use technology in the teaching-learning process but it is not happening in some places. When the study tried to identify, it came up to know that orphan schools are lacking which is the backdrop for children's development. So the paper has come up with the proposed ideas of imparting education i.e., teaching-learning through ICT tools.

With the help of ICT tools, the teaching-learning process becomes more easy and effective. Children are attracted to gadgets these days. This method of teaching attracts orphans and may change their perspective. Teenage is a very good age to mold the behavior of children. It builds confidence, communication, and their cognitive abilities.

The teenage orphans in the rural areas of the Telangana region would acquire new exposure to a learning environment with ICT methods of teaching and learning. They get the same level of education compared with their compatriots. Overall personality development will change and become more confident in speaking the English language. They may become career-oriented and participate in all activities or events confidently. They will know about online courses, English websites, speeches, the importance of English, and its opportunities. All these inputs enable them to improve their standard of living. They will acquire new exposure to teaching-learning through ICT methods. They will improve their personality development and overall holistic development.

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